

Towards Laminar Bizjets

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Laminarity is one of the most important technological path towards a significant drag reduction and aircraft aerodynamic efficiency.

Since the 80's, major experiments have been performed to validate the drag benefits of such a technology, either in flight or in wind tunnel, focusing on aerodynamic design: wing profile, adequate wing leading edge sweep angle, flight domain, with acceptable handling qualities.

Laminarity requires higher surface quality than existing manufacturing standards.

Dassault Aviation is participating in several aerodynamic research projects within Clean Sky 2 Airframe: BinCola (Laminar Horizontal Tail Plane and Nacelle Inlet wind tunnel test), Eulosam 2 (Low speed configuration of laminar aircraft wind tunnel model), Nacor (Laminar surface quality assessment by computation tools), and BLADE (Laminar Wing flight test on Airbus A340) initiated in Clean Sky.

Dassault Aviation's scope of research also encompasses key enablers such as manufacturing technologies and structural design. This multidisciplinary approach is particularly well illustrated by demonstration projects on laminar assembly and design such as ALFA (Laminar Horizontal Tail Plane ground demo), and BALANCE (Laminar inlet ground demo). Durability flight testing of specific laminar surface treatments are also performed to address the operational phase of the aircraft life cycle.

After introducing the laminarity interest and challenges, this presentation will describe Dassault Aviation's strategy towards laminar implementation on future bizjets, based on the contribution of the different projects listed above.